

Heart Sūtra

By Weiyu Lin, University of California, Berkeley

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The Heart Sūtra [Ch. Xinjing 心經; Skt. Prajñāpāramitāhṛdaya Sūtra; Tib. snying po'i mdo] is among the most popular Buddhist sūtras, notably in East Asia. It purports to be the essence, or the 'heart,' of the Perfection of Wisdom Sūtra [Skt. Prajñāpāramitā sūtras], a highly influential set of Mahāyāna sūtras known for the doctrine of emptiness (Skt. śūnyatā) which teaches that all entities lack intrinsic nature (Skt. svabhava) and that wisdom, in this sense, consists of a non-conceptual understanding of emptiness. The Heart Sūtra is known for its ability to transmit the profound wisdom of the Prajñāpāramitā sūtras in a succinct format. The most popular version in East Asia, believed to be a translation by Xuanzang 玄奘 (602-664) made in 649, consists of merely 260 characters. The Heart Sūtra opens with the statement that Avalokiteśvara understood the emptiness of all things and proceeds with the Bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara's sermon to Śāriputra, one of the Buddha's disciples. In this sermon, Avalokiteśvara foregrounds the teaching of the emptiness by systematically negates the major categories of Buddhist thought—including such seminal lists as the five aggregates, twelve sense-fields, and twelve links of dependent origination. Even nirvana is said to be ultimately empty. Its famous statement 'form is emptiness (śūnyatā), emptiness is form' is widely known in East Asia, even beyond Buddhist communities. The sūtra ends with a famous mantra of Prajñāpāramitā. This mantra, and the Heart Sūtra in general, are popularly used for protective purposes, and for this reason, the Heart Sūtra has been considered by some scholars not as a sūtra but a dhāraṇī, a Buddhist textual genre related to tantra that consists of incantations believed to possess amuletic power. In Tibetan context, the Heart Sūtra is often considered both a sūtra and tantra. There exist numerous tantric ritual manuals based on the Heart Sūtra, with Prajñāpāramitā being the goddess of worship. The Heart Sūtra encompasses two primary versions: the longer and the shorter. The longer version, favored in India, incorporates traditional Buddhist narrative framing, unlike the shorter version, which presents certain anomalies in comparison to typical Indian sutras. It features Avalokiteśvara, a deity of significant influence in China, with approximately 40% of its content being quotations from Nagarjuna's commentary on a Perfection of Wisdom sutra, and the remainder being original compositions. These textual irregularities, among others, led scholar Jan Nattier to speculate that the earliest translation of the shorter version, attributed to Kumārajīva, might have been a Chinese creation. This version is believed to have served as the foundation for Xuanzang's later translation. Given its profound impact across East Asia, the suggestion of its apocryphal origins carries considerable implications.

Date Range: 350 CE - 2024 CE

Region: East Asia, India, Central Asia, Tibet, Southeast Asia.

Region tags: Asia, Inner Asia

Area where Heart Sūtras have historically been read and used.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Fukui, Fumimasa 福井文雅. Hannya Shingyō no Rekishi-teki Kenkyū 般若心經の歴史的研究 [Study of the History of the Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra] (in Japanese, Chinese, and English). Tokyo: Shunjūsha 春秋社, 1987.
- Source 2: Lopez, Donald S. Jr. The Heart Sutra Explained: Indian and Tibetan Commentaries. New York: State University of New York Press, 1988. ISBN 0-88706-589-9.
- Source 3: Nattier, Jan. 'The Heart Sūtra: A Chinese Apocryphal Text?' Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies 15.2 (1992): 153-223.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://prajnaparamitahridaya.wordpress.com/about/>
- Source 1 Description: This helpful blogs compiles various versions of the Heart Sūtra in all major Buddhist languages.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.lotsawahouse.org/bo/words-of-the-buddha/heart-sutra>
- Source 2 Description: The Heart Sūtra in Tibetan and its English and French translation

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://cbetaonline.dila.edu.tw/zh/T0251>
- Source 1 Description: Xuanzang's Translation of the Heart Sūtra on the CBETA platform of Taisho Canon

– Source 2 URL: <https://library.bdrclibrary.org/search?q=%22%E0%BD%96%E0%BD%85%E0%BD%BC%E0%BD%98%E0%BC%8B%E0%BD%A3%E0%BE%A1%E0%BD%93%E0%BC%8B%E0%BD%A0>

– Source 2 Description: Tibetan Copies of the Heart Sūtra on the BDRCLibrary.org Database

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper
– Specify: The Heart Sūtra is among the most copied Buddhist texts and has thus been written on a variety of media.

– Wood

↳ Species
– Specify: Among Dunhuang manuscripts, there are several Heart Sūtra written on the wooden board. See Imre Galambos's video on this topic where he reveals a connection with European and Persian wooden boards.
Notes: https://youtu.be/l22LwR0ynj0?si=qc3lpGs-QO90X_ZC

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The Heart Sutra, due to its talismanic function, is sometimes copied onto small booklets or, in the case of the Dunhuang manuscripts, occasionally onto specially shaped wooden boards

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: it is important a Buddhist text is preserved as it is, so rarely does any modification take place

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– I don't know

↳ Cemetery
– I don't know

↳ Temple
– Yes

↳ Shrine
– Yes

↳ Altar
– Yes

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– I don't know

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– I don't know

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– I don't know

↳ Cave(s)
– Yes

Notes: The earliest datable evidence for the Shorter Version of the Heart Sūtra comes from a Chinese inscription of 661 found at Fangshan 房山, 12 years after its translation by Xuanzang.

↳ Hilltops
– I don't know

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– I don't know

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– I don't know

↳ Domestic contexts
– Yes

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Specify: Among Dunhuang manuscripts, there are over a hundred copies of the Heart Sūtras in both Tibetan and Chinese. The manuscripts are preserved in the so-called Library Cave which situates near the city of Dunhuang in today's Northwest China.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?
– Yes

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?
Select all that apply
– I don't know

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?
– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?
– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: According to the traditional historiography, the two most famous translations of the Heart Sūtra were done by Kumarajiva in the fifth century and Xuanzang in the seventh century. Both of their translation works are sponsored by the rulers. The Heart Sūtra, which includes several versions, are incorporated into the canon and has been reproduced numerous times as part of the canon – and the canon production is generally sponsored by the political rulers.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text itself does not stipulate any type of religious observance, but is itself often used as a talisman for personal use or for collective rituals. For instance, Amoghavajra in the eighth century has a Chinese transcription of the Sanskrit sound of the Heart Sūtra. We cannot ascertain the actual use of this particular text, but given Amoghavajra's role in the state-sponsored rituals, it is not inconceivable that the Heart Sūtra plays a role in the state-sponsored religious rituals.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sūtra could be produced as part of a canon, in which case it would be state-sponsored, or it could be copied individually. The latter case has been the most common way the Heart Sūtra has been reproduced, often carried out by professional scribes. These professional scribes, however, could be monastics (i.e., 'religious specialists' in this question) or lay Buddhists.

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Notes: As stated earlier, there are numerous ways by which the Heart Sūtra was copied. Other than professional scribes, the Heart Sūtra could also be copied out by lay Buddhists who are non-professional scribes but did so for the sake of merit-making.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No
 - Notes: The Heart Sūtra is popular across a vast swath of area in India, Central Asia, Tibet, China, Mongolia and Japan, thus encompassing a vast scope of ethnicities.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
 - Yes
 - Notes: In general, Buddhist monks are dedicated to the Buddhist cause through life, but they have the option of returning to the lay life.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?
 - Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Revealed by a high god?
 - No
 - ↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is revealed by Bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara to Śāriputra, one of the Buddha's disciples.
 - ↳ Inspired by high god?
 - Yes
 - Notes: In the Longer Heart Sūtra, we find a narrative framing that opens with the Buddha Sakyamuni entering the meditative state, before Bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara preached to Śāriputra. Hence, Avalokiteśvara could be understood as preaching on behalf of Buddha Sakyamuni
 - ↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The mantra at the end of the Heart Sūtra is referred to as 'the perfection of wisdom' (Prajñāpāramitā), which not only denotes the body of texts that the Heart Sutra is believed to be a concise summary of but also identifies Prajñāpāramitā as having been personified as a goddess. Therefore, Prajñāpāramitā can be viewed as an additional divine entity within the text.
 - ↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: Śāriputra, the recipient of the sermon, is the Buddha's disciple, and a human being. Śāriputra has a divine status for it is prophesized, not in the Heart Sūtra but in other Buddhist texts that, he'd become a buddha one day.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: There are several recensions of the Heart Sūtra that are the results of alternation of previous recensions, with the Shorter Heart Sūtra transmitted in East Asia being a significantly altered version. See Jayarava Attwood for its textual history. However, the alterations only become apparent against the long textual history of the Heart Sūtra. Otherwise, like all Buddhist sūtras, an alternation of the Heart Sūtra is not considered admissible.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– No

Notes: Institutions that interpret sūtras are integrated within the monastic community and are not separate entities tasked with this function. Specifically, it is the intellectual elites within these monasteries who produce commentaries. All commentaries on the Heart Sūtra were produced by monastics.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– Yes

Notes: Such sanction is not necessarily explicit, but more of a general norm. Typically, the individuals granted the authority to interpret and publicly lecture on a sūtra, such as the Heart Sūtra, are almost exclusively selected members of the monastic community. For each sūtra, certain commentaries are usually recognized as the most authoritative.

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

Notes: Yes. Yes. Given the numerous commentaries on the Heart Sūtra, some disagreement is to be expected. However, in this case, the disagreements do not seem particularly pronounced, as interpreters generally agree that the Heart Sūtra focuses on the teaching of emptiness. See Lopez, Donald S. Jr. (1988), *The Heart Sutra Explained: Indian and Tibetan Commentaries*, State Univ of New York Pr and McRae, John R. (1988), "Ch'an Commentaries on the Heart Sutra". *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies*. 11 (2): 87-115.

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– I don't know

Notes: Debate conventions among Buddhist exegetes vary with cultural context (e.g., Indian, Chinese, Tibetan). Despite this, disagreements on the Heart Sūtra are relatively minor, making it unclear whether there are systematic debates surrounding these issues.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

Notes: The known commentators and lecturers on the Heart Sūtra are dominantly male, but as it is the case for Buddhist Sūtras in general, the transmission of these texts could also be undertaken by nuns.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

Notes: The Heart Sūtra is widely transmitted across Asia in various linguistic spheres.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: Sanskrit, Chinese, Tibetan, Chinese transliteration of Sanskrit, Tangut, Mongolian, Manchu, Uyghur, just some examples.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: No matter the language into which the Heart Sūtra is translated, the mantra is always rendered in the transliteration of Sanskrit, for the mantra is believed to possess potency in its very sound.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Notes: The only instance favoring a 'yes' response would be the fact that the Heart Sūtra represents one of the only two sūtras in Chinese Buddhism whose Sanskrit sounds have been transcribed in full into Chinese characters.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

Notes: Māhāyāna Buddhist texts were predominantly written in Sanskrit. Hence, as the original language of most sūtras translated to local languages, it is held in high esteem. This reverence is all the more pronounced in the case of dharani and mantras which are believed to possess magical powers. For a history of Sanskrit study in China and Japan, see Siddham: An Essay on the History of Sanskrit Studies in China and Japan by H van Gulik

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sūtra has been translated into numerous languages, including Chinese and Tibetan. While these languages serve as common means of communication, they are also considered religious languages in their own right, each with its own linguistic specificities. The Heart Sūtra has been translated into numerous languages, including Chinese and Tibetan. While these languages serve as common means of communication, they are also considered religious languages in their own right. When used in a religious context, they exhibit their own linguistic specificities.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sūtra is widely memorized by Buddhists. Sermons on the Heart Sūtra, as it is the case in general for sūtra sermons, could be considered an instance of oral transmission.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text is popular across the entire geographical area encompassed by Mahāyāna Buddhism

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sūtra itself does not encourage the act of disseminating the text, but it is typical of Mahāyāna sūtras to include such exhortation of copying and transmitting the texts. This exhortation section is designated in Chinese Buddhist exegesis as 'circulation section': 流通分

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Copying sūtras is one of the most popular ways of accumulating merits for the sake of this-life and future-life benefits, including rebirth in a pure land. Contemplating on the sūtra also has the spiritual merit of facilitating one's achievement of enlightenment.

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: it is typical of Mahāyāna sūtras to include such exhortation of copying and transmitting the texts. This exhortation section is designated in Chinese Buddhist exegesis as 'circulation section.' 流通分. In the Heart Sutra itself, however, no such exhortation to circulate exists.

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that in different eras, specific texts are said to appear in the world to intervene at precise moments. This belief is prevalent in Buddhist traditions with a strong 'revelation' component, such as the Tibetan 'hidden treasure' tradition, as well as in beliefs concerning the disappearance of the dharma.

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing, while taking place primarily in human realm, always applies to the realms of gods, semi-gods and hell beings.

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: Although the Heart sūtra does not exhort proselytization, it is typical of Mahāyāna sūtras to include such exhortation of copying and transmitting the texts. This exhortation section is designated in Chinese Buddhist exegesis as 'circulation section.' 流通分

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– I don't know

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– I don't know

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

- ↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
 - Specify: The Heart Sūtra is often used as a dharani text. In Tibetan Buddhism, it is classified both as a discursive sūtra and a tantra which is a genre of texts with heavy emphasis on tantric rituals. The Heart Sūtra could be used in a variety of ritual contexts, often with an emphasis on the worship of Goddess Prajñāpāramitā, whose mantra appears at the end of the Heart Sūtra. Below I will provide an example of a Tangut tantric ritual based on the heart sūtra. For the details, see Shen Weirong, 'On the Integration of Chinese, Tibetan, Exoteric and Esoteric Buddhism in the Tangut Kingdom.' In this ritual, the Heart Sutra plays a central role as practitioners create a sacred space, offer prayers, and make offerings to the Saintly Mother of Prajñāpāramitā. The ritual involves cleaning and preparing a tranquil space, placing a statue of the Saintly Mother, and making offerings. Practitioners then recite the Heart Sutra, focusing on visualizations of the Saintly Mother and a celestial assembly, to cleanse sins and obstacles, and to imbue themselves with the blessings and wisdom of Prajñāpāramitā. This recitation, which can be repeated multiple times depending on the practitioner's capacity, is believed to bring about profound spiritual benefits, including protection by deities, accumulation of merit, and eventual enlightenment. However, while this example emphasizes the tantric use of the Heart Sūtra, its use is widespread and highly flexible.
- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
 - Yes
- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Yes
- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - I don't know
- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
 - Specify: The Heart Sūtra is used on a variety of rituals, including daily practices. In an example cited earlier, the Heart Sūtra is exactly used as a daily practice.
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Buddhist ritual often amalgamates a variety of practices which could be practiced in the same sequence.
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
 - I don't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?
– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?
– No

↳ Can it be touched?
– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?
– I don't know

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?
– Yes

Notes: For instance, in the example below, the Heart Sūtra is arranged in the shape of a stūpa. It is not clear the exact function of such textual arrangement of the Heart Sūtra, but some kind of esoteric function is suspected.

↳ Promotes knowledge?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?
– Yes

Notes: The sūtra ends with a famous mantra of Prajñāpāramitā. This mantra, and the Heart Sūtra in general, are popularly used for protective purposes, and for this reason, the Heart Sūtra has been considered by some scholars not as a sūtra but a dhāraṇī, a Buddhist textual genre related to tantra that consists of incantations believed to possess amuletic power.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?
– Yes

↳ Physical healing
– Yes

↳ Mental/psychological healing
– I don't know

↳ Incubation
– No

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
– Yes

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
– Yes

Notes: The sūtra ends with a famous mantra of Prajñāpāramitā. This mantra, and the Heart Sūtra in general, are popularly used for protective purposes, and for this reason, the Heart Sūtra has been considered by some scholars not as a sūtra but a dhāraṇī, a Buddhist textual genre that consists of incantations believed to possess amuletic power.

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
– Yes

Notes: Below are two examples where materiality are altered. Both are from Dunhuang manuscripts.

- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: In the example of 2168, the text is shaped in the form of stupa.
- ↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?
 - Please specify the substances in the sub-questions
 - I don't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sūtra contains two major versions -- the Larger and Shorter versions. The Longer Version is popular in India and Tibet, whereas the shorter version is popular in China, Tibet and Japan. The Shorter Version has increasingly been suspected of being a Chinese apocryphon. The Longer and Shorter Version in turn has multiple sub-versions. For instance, in Chinese Buddhist canon, there are three versions of the Shorter Version (T250 and T251 and T256) and five Extended Version: T252, T254, T255, T257. Each version is deemed authoritative. For a textual history, see Nattier, Jan (1992), "The Heart Sūtra: A Chinese Apocryphal Text?", *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies*, 15 (2): 153-223, and Attwood, Jayarava. 'Preliminary Notes on the Extended Heart Sutra in Chinese.' *Asian Literature and Translation* 8.1 (2021): 63-85.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: For traditional Chinese Buddhists, they are aware of the multiple versions of the Heart Sūtra, notably including the one translated by Kumarajiva in the fifth century and the one by Xuanzang in the early seventh century.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: The numerous versions differ slightly. See Jayarava Attwood's 'Preliminary Notes on the Extended Heart Sutra in Chinese.' Especially page 79 for a diagram tracing the textual history. The Longer Version differs from the Shorter Version in that the former has a narrative framing.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

Notes: For instance, in a ritual attested in a Tangut ritual manual, it is a specific version translated by Dehui that is used for the Heart Sutra ritual. See Shen Weirong's article 'On the Integration of Chinese, Tibetan, Exoteric and Esoteric Buddhism in the Tangut Kingdom'

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: In Chinese Buddhist canon, for instance, there are three short and five long versions, all of which are deemed authoritative. However, the most popular one is the one supposedly translated by Xuanzang. Its popularity however doesn't compromise the authority of the other

versions. The Longer Version primarily differs from the Shorter Version in that it provides a narrative framing.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

— Yes

Notes: It purports to be the essence, or the 'heart,' of the Prajñāpāramitā sūtras, a highly influential set of Mahāyāna sūtras known for the doctrine of emptiness (Skt. śūnyatā). Prajñāpāramitā sūtras, in turn, are part of the Mahāyāna Buddhist canons.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

— Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

— Yes

Notes: 1. The texts supposedly record the teachings of the Buddha; 2. Commentaries and treatises written by Indian masters; 3. Commentaries and treatises written by well-known the masters of the recipient cultures (e.g., Tibet, China, Japan). Traditional Buddhists were always cautious of apocryphal sūtras which they sought identify and remove from the canon.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

— Yes

Notes: It fluctuates through the ages and kept incorporating new content. On the history of the formation of Chinese Buddhist canon, see the edited volume *Spreading Buddha's Word in East Asia*. Regarding the open nature of the canon, see 'Notions and Visions of the Canon in Early Chinese Buddhism' by Stefano Zacchetti.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

— Yes

Notes: The Heart Sūtra in Tibetan Buddhist canon, for instance, has been classified as both a discursive sutra belonging to the Prajñāpāramitā sūtras collection, but also to the tantric collection. This classification hinges on the interpretation of the nature of the Heart Sūtra. A similar tendency is observed in Nepali Buddhism. See 'The Heart Sūtra as Dhāraṇī' by Jonathan Silk.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

— Yes

Notes: The Heart Sūtra is the shortest text of the Prajñāpāramitā Collection which contains a series of other Prajñāpāramitā with varying length.

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

—Specify: The Heart Sūtra is said to be the summary of the prajnaparamita sūtras which make up the 'Prajna Collection' in Chinese Buddhist canon.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

— No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

—Other [specify]: In this sūtra, Avalokiteśvara foregrounds the teaching of the emptiness by systematically negates the major categories of Buddhist thought—including such seminal lists as the five aggregates, twelve sense-fields, and twelve links of dependent origination. These lists could be considered the index of fundamental Buddhist teachings.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

— Yes

Notes: There is a lineage construction regarding the transmission of the larger Prajñāpāramitā sūtras. However, the Heart Sūtra itself does not indicate a chain of lineage, other than indicating that it was taught by Avalokiteśvara to Sariputra on behalf of the Buddha. However, it is important to note that The Heart Sutra is the only major Prajñāpāramitā text in which Avalokiteśvara appear which indicate a special origin of the Heart Sūtra in relation to the other Prajñāpāramitā sūtras

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

— No

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?
– No

↳ How is the lineage established?
– Intellectual Elect

Does the text express a formal legal code?
– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?
– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?
– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?
– Yes

Notes: For instance, 'there is no birth and no death.' 不生不滅. This could be interpreted as a negation of the process of generating (e.g, birth) and ceasing (e.g., death). By negating it, however, it also assumes the normative Buddhist belief in reincarnation.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

Notes: It doesn't explicitly state it, but the belief in a pure land may have been in the background. This takes into account that the Heart Sutra is the only major Prajñāpāramitā text in which Avalokiteśvara appear which indicate a special origin of the Heart Sūtra in relation to the other Prajñāpāramitā sūtras, suggesting that it was written when the cult of Avalokiteśvara was popular, textually associated with the twenty-fourth chapter of the Lotus Sutra and with the Pure Land sutras which involve beliefs in pure lands.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?
– No

Notes: Notes: For instance, 'there is no birth and no death.' 不生不滅. This could be interpreted as a negation of the process of generating (e.g, birth) and ceasing (e.g., death). By negating it, however, it also assumes the normative Buddhist belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?
– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?
– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?
– No

Are formal burials present in the text?
– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?
– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?
– Yes

Notes: Namely, the Buddha and the Bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara. However, in the Longer Version, only

the Buddha is present, whereas in the Shorter Version, Avalokiteśvara is the main preacher, with Buddha's presence presumed by not explicitly stated.

↳ A supreme high-god is present
– No

Previously human spirits are present
– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present
– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?
– Yes

Notes: Sariputra, whom Avalokitesvara address to, is a human but is prophesized to be a Buddha in a future life – hence, he may be considered a human-divine being.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?
– I don't know

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?
– Yes

Notes: Avalokitesvara communicates orally with Sariputra. The setting is not specified, but is implied in the everyday environment in the human realm.

↳ In dreams?
– No

↳ In trance possession?
– No

↳ Through divination practices?
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?
– No

↳ Only through monarch?
– No

↳ Other?
– Specify: no

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?
– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?
– Yes

Notes: Avalokiteśvara is visible to Sariputra.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the Lower Version, Buddha Sakyamuni is not explicitly mentioned, but it is assumed that Avalokiteśvara delivers the sermon on the behalf of the Buddha.

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: no

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: implied in the line 'transform all sufferings' 度一切苦厄

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - No
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Notes: a sense of reverence is implied towards the mantra

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: wisdom in the sense of the understanding of 'emptiness'

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A nation-state

Notes: If we follow Nattier's thesis that the Shorter Heart Sūtra was composed in China, then Kumarjiva's version of the Heart Sūtra was composed during Northern and Southern Dynasties when China was divided into nation states.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A state

Notes: The 'nation-state' and 'empire' option also apply, depending on the period of Chinese history in discussion.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A state

Notes: There are a number of persecutions in Chinese Buddhist history initiated by the emperor.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist monasteries, especially via public sermons.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: The text doesn't say it, but the teaching of Buddhist scriptures in general is restricted to Buddhist clergies.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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